

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D3.2 PreMETS digital certificate/credential V1.1

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Abstract

The aim of this offering is to help learners and professionals acquire specific skills through flexible and progressive certifications tailored to industry needs. The certificates are issued via the PreMETS digital platform and are in line with the European Digital Credential for Learning, although full compliance with the requirements requires a legal entity for digital seals, which the project currently lacks. The framework aims to address skills gaps in industries such as transport and manufacturing by providing industry-relevant training through stackable micro-credentials.

1. Overview

The PreMETS project, which is part of the ERASMUS+ initiative, focuses on the development of education and training systems for predictive maintenance (PM), an area that is crucial for preventing equipment failure and optimizing resource use. As part of WP3, the project is developing a micro-certificate certification framework to help learners and professionals improve their skills in predictive maintenance. This framework will offer incrementally customizable certificates based on industry needs, allowing individuals to progressively upskill. It is also integrated into a digital learning platform that supports flexible learning and closes skills gaps in predictive maintenance in various industries such as aerospace, manufacturing and the energy sector. This system of micro-credentials is designed to facilitate access to training and increase relevance to industry by promoting the flow of knowledge between education, research and industry. It promotes sustainable, innovative approaches to maintenance and is in line with European goals for economic and environmental resilience.

2. European Digital Credential for Learning

The European Digital Credential for Learning¹ is part of the Europass initiative, which aims to support the validation and recognition of learning achievements across Europe. It enables educational institutions, employers and learners to easily issue, receive and exchange digital certificates, simplifying the certification process. Each credential is digitally signed with a digital seal to guarantee the authenticity of the certification. These are forgery-proof and can be checked immediately via the Europass system.

PreMETS has developed its own platform for the provision of digital credentials, which is closely based on the Europass model. However,

¹ <https://europass.europa.eu/en/europass-tools/european-digital-credentials>

as there is no digital seal, the certificates issued by PreMETS do not fully comply with the EDC standards. Despite this limitation, the system issues i) a standalone XML certificate file that learners can download and share, and ii) provides a verification service to confirm the validity of the certificate.

The certificates are based on the EU's free Europass Digital Credentials App. More specifically, the development of the certification process is embedded in the PreMETS platform and includes the availability of the online course on the PreMETS platform as well as an automatic function on the number of correct answers (70% - 80%). However, it is not possible to follow the European Digital Credentials for Learning (Figure 1) as a digital seal is required. A digital seal must be acquired by a legal entity and the PreMETS project does not have such facilities.

Figure 1: European Digital Credentials for Learning

Source: <https://europass.europa.eu/en/how-issue-european-digital-credentials>

3. Certificate Development

The PreMETS project aims to develop a flexible and dynamic certification system tailored to the needs of the predictive maintenance (PM) sector. This system is designed to support the validation of skills and competencies through micro-credentials that are both modular and stackable. The certificates are issued digitally through the PreMETS platform and provide learners with verified, incremental recognition of their achievements.

The PreMETS platform (<https://premets-platform.eu/>), which follows the main features of the European Digital Credential, provides suitable certificates for predictive maintenance as depicted in Figure 4. The framework for the certification is also adopted (Deliverable 3.1) to deliver a standalone XML certificate file and a verification service (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Certificate of Completion

Figure 3: Certificate of Completion

The UML diagram (Figure 4) outlines the main processes for certification. More specifically,

1. **Course Enrollment:**

The process begins when a learner enrolls in a specific course (TN/WN). These courses consist of several sections, each containing learning materials and assessments.

2. **Section Progression:**

After enrollment, the learner proceeds to complete individual sections of the course (e.g., TN1/WN1, TN2/WN2, etc.). Each section typically follows these steps:

- **Watch Video Lectures:** Learners watch lectures to gain foundational knowledge.
- **Study Materials:** Supplementary materials (e.g., booklets, slides) are provided for in-depth study.
- **Practice Quiz:** After studying, learners attempt a practice quiz to assess understanding before taking the final quiz.
- **Final Quiz:** After the practice phase, a final quiz must be passed to complete the section.
- **Section Certification:** If the learner has passed the final quiz for a section, they will receive the certification for that section (e.g., Certification for TN1/WN1).

3. **Final Course Certification**

Once all sections of the course have been completed and the respective section quizzes have been passed, learners can take a final course quiz. If they pass this, they will receive a certificate of completion for the entire course.

This modular certification approach enables micro-credentials at both the section and course level and provides learners with flexible and progressive recognition of their skills.

Figure 4: UML diagram of Certification Process